

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Work Engagement and Employee Retention of Deposit Money Banks in Ebonyi State

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Abstract

The study evaluated the work engagement and employee retention of deposit money banks in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between leadership skills and employee development; and evaluate the relationship between communication and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state. The area of the study was the selected and international recognized banks in Abakiliki Metropolis in Ebonyi state. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The population of the study was seven hundred and twenty seven (728) staff. Ferund and Williams formula was used to get the sample size of Two hundred and fifty two (252) at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and thirty five (235) staff returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool. The findings indicated Leadership skills had significant position with relationship with employee development, $Z(95, n = 235), 7.453 < 8.627, P < .05$ and Communication had significant positive relationship with employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state $Z(95, n = 235), 5.414 < 7.061, P < .05$. The study concluded that leadership skills and communication had significant position with relationship with employee development and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state. The study recommended among others that the management should endeavor to possess leadership skills for effective problem solving in the organizations and the opportunity to develop goods and services that set the firm apart from rivals and creating a competitive advantage.

Keywords: Work Engagement; Employee Retention; Leadership Skills; Employee Morale

Introduction

Long working hours, excessive workloads, and high expectations lead to decreased productivity and engagement. Everyone wants an engaged workforce. It is the blueprint for success. Especially in these uncertain times when it is hard to predict which way the economy is heading. Just ensure that employees are fully motivated and engaged, and ride out any storm (Sinclair, 2023).

Work engagement today has become synonymous with terms like 'employee experience' and 'employee satisfaction'. The relevance is much more due to the vast majority of new generation professionals in the workforce who have a higher propensity to be 'distracted' and 'disengaged' at work (StaffConnect, 2022). Work engagement is the extent to which employees feel passionate about their jobs, are committed to the organization, and put discretionary effort into their work. When organizations focus on how to improve employee satisfaction, changes won't necessarily lead to increased performance. Oftentimes, the conditions that make employees "satisfied" with their jobs are the same conditions that frustrate high performing employees. Top performers embrace change, search out ways to improve, and challenge the status quo. They search out feedback from management, expect all employees be held accountable for delivering results, find meaning with their team and at work, whereas low performers avoid accountability, cling to the status quo, and resist change (Custom Insight, 2022).

Work engagement is considered as the positive antithesis of burnout. Contrary to those who suffer from burnout, engaged employees have a sense of energetic and effective connection with their work; instead of stressful and demanding they look upon their work as challenging. Accordingly, engagement is characterized by energy, involvement and efficacy, which constitute the direct opposites of the three burnout dimensions – exhaustion, cynicism, and reduced accomplishment (Maslach & Leiter, 1997; Schaufeli, 2012).

Work engagement is *positive behavior or a positive state of mind at work that leads to positive work-related outcomes*. Work engagement is the "harnessing of organization member's selves to their work roles: in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, emotionally and mentally during role performances". Three aspects of work motivation are cognitive, emotional and physical engagement. Employee engagement describes the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Engaged employees care about their work and about the performance of the company and feel that their efforts make a difference. An engaged employee is in it for more than a paycheck and may consider their well-being linked to their performance, and thus instrumental to their company's success (Smith,2023), The unable for banks and firms to meet up with work engagement have led to Low employee engagement which is when employees do not feel emotionally connected and invested in their work. They tend to be less productive, have commitment issues, and are less likely to stay with the organization. Low morale levels, decreased motivation, lack of employee satisfaction, increased absenteeism and turnover.

Statement of the Study

Work engagement is positive behavior or a positive state of mind at work that leads to positive work-related outcomes. Employees with high levels of work engagement are energetic and dedicated to their work and immersed to their work. It is outlining a path for growth that will keep employees engaged and help you retain top talent. Plus, offer support and training in the form of stipends or bursaries to help employees get there.

The work environment is supposed to provide a smooth work experience where employees can get things done easily with minimum stress. But unfortunately, things have fallen apart. Banks and other organizations have problems of Employee reward, recognition, leadership skills, communication skills, Choosing the wrong tools & technology, not having, and sticking to your engagement strategy, Recruiting the wrong people, etc. which are at the heart of impactful employee engagement strategies and high levels of retention.

On the other hand, not having an employee recognition program in place will leave workers demotivated and dissatisfied with banks or organizations. The consequences if not handled will lead to lack of communication flow

and recognition, low commitment and morale, lack of motivation, and trust. This has necessitated the study work engagement and employee retention of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the work engagement and employee retention of deposit money banks in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between leadership skills and employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between communication and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between leadership skills and employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state?
- ii. What is the relationship between communication and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Leadership has relationship skills with employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state.
- ii. communication has relationship with employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Work

Organizations provided jobs, and employees showed up to do them. It was a very transactional process. We are moving towards a world where work is about an experience, a relationship, and doing something with a sense of purpose. Work is about doing something you want to do every day, not drudgery. Organizations are starting to invest in designing employee experiences, new technologies are being added and promoted in the workplace, and the focus is on creating great corporate cultures (Morgan,2015). 'Meaning at work' refers to someone's work environment, such as their team or the organizations purpose. Whereas 'meaningful work' refers to the purpose or significant value the work task provides an individual (Sayle, 2023).

Engagement

Engagement *refers to the degree of attention, interest, curiosity, motivation and passion students show*, as well as the effort and time they invest. A term which is used to describe the technique or result to encourage a company's customers to interact and share their experiences with the communication contents, cultural artefacts, an advertised brand, or the company (Roque & Raposo, 2021). Engagement refers to the ability of a brand to generate engagement with its consumers through persistent and stable relationships. The better the relationship with the client, the better to get to know consumers or clients and provide a differential value that improves their positioning and perception as a brand. Engagement is an effect, a reaction, a connection, a response and/or an experience of customers with

each other, with a company or with a brand. The initiative of engagement or commitment can be either of the consumer or of the company, and the means of this can be online or offline (Arimetrics, 2023).

Work Engagement

Work engagement is the "harnessing of organization members to their work roles: in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, emotionally and mentally during role performances". Three aspects of work motivation are cognitive, emotional and physical engagement. The concept of work engagement fits into the tradition of positive psychology, a field in psychology which focuses on ways to increase wellbeing; rather than diagnosing or treating mental illness. (Oshwiki, 2017). Work engagement refers to a positive, affective-motivational state of high energy combined with high levels of dedication and a strong focus on work (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2010 Cited by Bakker & Albrecht, 2018).

Components of Work Engagement used in the Study

Leadership Skills

Leadership is the ability of an individual or group of people to influence and guide followers or members of an organization, society or team. Leadership often is an attribute tied to a person's title, seniority or ranking in a hierarchy. However, it is an attribute anyone can have or attain, even those without leadership positions. It is developable skills that can be improved over time (Barney & Pratt, 2023). Leadership is the art of motivating a group of people to act toward achieving a common goal. In a business setting, this can mean directing workers and colleagues with a strategy to meet the company's needs (Ward, 2023).

Communication

Communication is the actionable transfer of information from one person, group, or place to another by writing, speaking, or using a medium that provides a means of understanding. Every communication consists of a minimum of one sender, a receiver, and a message. The transmission of a message from sender to recipient risks being affected by many things because communication impacts how people interact. These include the location, medium used to communicate, the cultural situation, and the emotions involved. However, communication helps people to interact and share various aspects of life (Ntara, 2023). Communication is the process of sending and receiving messages through verbal or nonverbal means, including speech, or oral communication; writing and graphical representations (such as infographics, maps, and charts); and signs, signals, and behavior. More simply, communication is said to be "the creation and exchange of meaning" (Nordquist, 2019).

Employee

An employee is someone that another person or company hires to perform a service. Business owners compensate employees for their work to grow and maintain their business. Employees typically have a specified pay rate and a written or implied employment contract with the party they work for (Indeed, 2024). An **employee** is a worker hired by an employer to do a specific job. Employers control how employees are paid, when employees work, and how employees work (Heathfield, 2022).

Retention

Retention is defined as the process by which a company ensures that its employees don't quit their jobs. Every company and industry has a varying retention rate, which indicates the percentage of employees who remained with the organization during a fixed period (BasuMallick, 2021). Retention is a voluntary move by an organization to create an environment which engages employees for a long term, the most important purpose of retention is to look for ways to prevent the capable workers from quitting the organization as this could have negative effect on productivity and profitability. The view that the main purpose of retention is primarily for organizational gains is similarly viewed by Humphreys et al. (2009), who in describing the concept, place the focus of retention in terms of

“some notion of adequacy or sufficiency of length of service, which can be measured in terms of a return on the costs of investment associated with training and recruitment or the effects on patient care that are considered to be optimal (Ukessays, 2021).

Employee Retention

Employee retention refers to an organization's ability to retain quality employees. The retention rate is often expressed as a percentage and the goal is for it to be high (Herrity, 2023). Employee retention is a phenomenon where employees choose to stay on with their current company and don't actively seek other job prospects. Employee retention is defined as an organization's ability to prevent [employee turnover](#), or the number of people who leave their job in a certain period, either voluntarily or involuntarily. Increasing employee retention has a direct impact on business performance and success. The opposite of retention is turnover, where employees leave the company for a variety of reasons ([BasuMallick, 2021](#)).

Components of Employee Retention used in the Study

Employee Development

Employee development is a process of helping employees progress in their careers by acquiring new skills. Its goal is to improve the existing competencies of your employees and helping them to develop new ones, all with the aim of supporting your business goals. Sure, employee development involves investment (Terpiłowski, 2021).

Employee development is a process of improving employees' existing competencies and skills and developing newer ones to support the organization's goals (Valamis, 2023).

Employee Morale

Employee morale, often known as workplace morale, refers to the general well-being of the people who work in that environment. Employee morale encourages cohesiveness in a company, which results in team morale or staff morale, making accomplishing organizational goals easier. One may see a direct correlation between it and production. Workplace morale is a combination of how employees feel about coming to work each day, how they go about doing their jobs, and how they view the company's plans. Job happiness, outlook on life, and attitude all come together in this concept. Staff morale is generally higher than the morale of their counterparts if the individual is content and motivated at work (Burtler, 2023). Employee morale can be defined as the level of enthusiasm and job satisfaction that employees feel about their work. It is an essential indicator of a worker's motivation and commitment to the organization and reflects upon how they perceive their role in the workplace. It is determined by factors such as communication between management and staff, working conditions, opportunities for growth and development, salary, benefits, and recognition (Vreede, 2023).

Conceptual Framework

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Vroom's expectancy theory by Vroom (1964). Vroom's expectancy theory was an attempt to describe how an individual's motivation to achieve a particular goal or performance target can be explained in terms of what outcome would become beneficial to the individual as a result of achieving that goal and what value is placed on that outcome" (Banjoko 2002). The theory explains how an individual perceives or understands the relationship between effort, performance and rewards. Vroom centered on those factors involved in stimulating or prompting an individual to put in more effort into something as this was the basis for motivation. He identified three factors each based on the individual's perception of the situation; they are:

- a) **Expectancy:** this refers to the extent to which the individual believes that a particular action will produce a particular result.
- b) **Instrumentality:** this refers to the extent to which the individual believes that effective performance will lead to desired results.
- c) **Valence:** this refers to the strength of the belief that those attractive rewards are actually available.

Empirical Review

Leadership Skills and Employee Development

Nwakoby, Okoye, & Anugwu (2019) conducted a study on the effect of organizational culture on employee performance in deposit money banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intent to: ascertain the extent bureaucratic culture has significant influence on employees' performance of deposit money banks and determine whether innovative culture has significant influence on employees' performance of deposit money banks. Survey research design was employed for this study. The data were collected through the questionnaires administered to the respondents. The formulated hypotheses were tested with regression analysis. The result shows that bureaucratic culture does not significantly affect employee performance of deposit money banks. Another finding is that innovative culture has significant affect employee performance of deposit money banks.

Ugwu (2021) conducted a study on the leadership supportiveness and employee punctuality of the deposit money banks in Enugu State. Ten (10) selected Banks were used for the study out of 21 registered banks in Nigeria. The banks were chosen with no number of branches in Enugu metropolis and staff. These banks include: United Bank of Africa (UBA), Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB), Union Bank, ECOBANK, Fidelity Bank, Access Bank, First Bank, and First City

Monument Bank (FCMB), Zenith Bank, and Polaris Bank. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool. The findings indicated that the relationship between leadership effective communication and employee ability to complete a required task is significantly, the relationship between the frequency of leadership seeking out feedback and employee time reliability of deposit money banks was significantly high, and that the relationship between leadership democracy and employee trustworthiness of deposit money banks in Enugu state was significantly high. The study concluded that leadership effective communication, frequency of leadership seeking out feedback and leadership democracy had high significant relationship with employee ability to complete a required task, employee time reliability and employee trustworthiness of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Opadeyi and Akpa (2021) conducted a study to examine the effect of career development and employee engagement in selected Deposit Money Banks in Ogun State. A cross-sectional survey research design was utilized for this study. Primary data was sourced using a structured and self- consisted of employees of the four selected deposit money banks (United Bank of Africa, Zenith Bank Plc, Access Bank Plc and Guaranty Trust Bank) located in Ogun state, Nigeria which amounts to 1630 employees. A sample size for the study was given as (419) using the research advisors table of sample size. The data gathered was analyzed using descriptive statistics and simple linear regression analysis. The findings revealed that there is a positive and significant effect of career development on employee engagement ($R=0.686$, $R^2 = 0.471$, $F = 343.129$, $p<0.005$). The study concluded that career development significantly contributes towards employee engagement in selected deposit money banks in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Marcus & Ekperi (2023) conducted a study on the effect of political environment on performance in selected deposit money banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study was aimed at determining the extent to which political instability affects goal attainment in selected deposit money banks in Enugu State. A sample size of 300 was used for the study. Out of the 300 copies of questionnaires that were distributed, 282 copies were correctly filled and returned while 18 copies were not returned. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The hypotheses were tested using simple linear regression statistical tools. The findings indicate that Political instability negatively affected goal attainment in selected deposit money banks in Enugu state ($r = 0.874$; $t = 5.986$; $F = 1248.625$; $p < 0.05$). Political interference negatively affected employee performance and employee satisfaction in selected deposit money banks in Enugu state ($r = 0.919$; $t = 8.646$; $F = 1524.624$; $p < 0.05$). Government policies and regulation had significant negative impact on productivity in selected deposit money banks in Enugu state ($r = 0.874$; $t = 8.053$; $F = 902.444$; $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that political environment had a significant negative effect on performance in selected deposit money banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

lyke-Ofoedu, Okafor and Ogbuagu (2023) examined the effect of career development techniques on employee performance in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The research design employed in this study was the descriptive survey research design. The sample size of 231 respondents was drawn from population of the study which consists of 548 employees of Wema Bank Plc, Sterling Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc and Access Bank Plc in Enugu State. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses stated were tested using single regression analysis. The empirical result shows that there is a positive and significant effect of induction training on employee quality of service delivery (t-statistics (58.161) > critical value (0.000)). Again, the study revealed that there is a positive and significant effect of job rotation on employee punctuality (t-statistics (59.146) > critical value (0.000)). The study also revealed that there is a positive and significant effect of formal education on employee transparency (t-statistics (53.984) > critical value (0.000)).

Communication and Employee Morale

Ayogu (2018) conducted a study on the employee empowerment on quality service delivery in the Nigeria banking industry. Employee empowerment is a very important issues to organizations especially those providing services. This is because the customers and employees are engaged simultaneously in the production of service. The inability of the management to control the services encounter makes the employees responsible for the quality of service delivered to the customers. This practice can directly affect the quality of service. The objective of this study is thus to determine the impact employee empowerment has on service quality delivery in the Nigeria banking industry. The study covered four branches of First Bank in Enugu Metropolis. This is because the four branches are within Enugu State metropolis and so, there was easy access. The sample size consisted of all the staff in the various branches with the exception of contract (in sourcing) staff. The study used primary and secondary data, Questionnaires were distributed to two hundred employees across the branches of first bank and regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected for the study. Out of the 200 questionnaires distributed fifteen (15) were not returned. The study found out that employee empowerment has positive and significant impact on the service quality.

Mbah, Nwatu & Okwor (2021) examined the effect of compensation on employee performance in deposit money banks in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: (i) evaluate the effect of wage and salary compensation on employee quality of service delivery in deposit money banks in South East, Nigeria. (ii) Ascertain the effect of retirement benefit compensation on employee punctuality in deposit money banks in South East, Nigeria. (iii) Determine the effect of fringe benefits compensation on employee transparency in deposit money banks in South East, Nigeria. The research design of the study was descriptive survey research method. The sample size of 371 respondents was drawn from population of the study which consists of 5168 management staff of deposit money banks /commercial banks licensed by Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in South East Research questions were answered using frequency table, mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using single regression. The findings of the study revealed that there is a positive and significant effect of wage and salary compensation has positive significant effect on employee quality of service delivery in deposit money bank in South-east Nigeria (t-statistics (43.312) > P-value (0.000)); there is a positive and significant effect of retirement benefit compensation has positive significant effect on employee punctuality in deposit money bank in South-east Nigeria (t-statistics (48.491)

> P-value (0.000), it also revealed that there is a positive and significant effect of fringe benefits compensation has positive significant effect on employee transparency in deposit money bank in South-east Nigeria (t-statistics (52.292) > P-value (0.000).

Nweke & Obinichi-Aaron (2022) conducted a study on *the influence of communication guidelines on employees' job efficiency in money deposit banks in Port Harcourt metropolis*. The research design that was adopted in the study is the descriptive research design. The population of the study was 10 which consisted of professional employees in commercial banks in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The banks investigated include, The banks investigated include, GT Bank, NTA, by Location junction, Heritage Bank, Rumuola, Fidelity Bank, Aba Road, by GRA Junction, FCMB, GRA junction Port Harcourt, First Bank Rumuola, Heritage Bank Rumuola, GT Bank Nnamdi Azikiwe Road Branch, Access Bank, Rumukurushi junction, Fidelity Bank, Rumuola, UBA Rumuokwuta, FCMB, by Kala Police Station all put together to employees and their assistants in each of the branches amounted to one (1) employee per branch. The sample size of 10 was used adopting the purposive sampling technique which implies that the entire population was studied. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaires. The questionnaire was administered personally by the researcher. Out of the 10 copies of questionnaire distributed, only 8 representing 98% were duly completed and returned. The study based its analysis on the returned percentage. The study used simple percentages to answer the three-research question and Chi-Square to test the null hypotheses. The study concluded that there are external, internal and social media communication policies significantly influence job performance of employees. Money deposit banks put the communication policies in place in order to safeguard information goodwill of the bank and staff discrete conducts on organizational matters.

Nnadi, Ezeh & Nduka (2022) conducted a study on the influence of job security on the profitability deposit money Banks in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: examine the influence terms of an employment contract on the reduced expenses; evaluate the influence of collective bargaining agreement on the net interest margin and identify the influence of range of task on the inventory velocity of deposit money Banks in Enugu State. The study was based on the three (3) selected banks within Enugu metropolis with high number of staff and long years of establishment namely: First bank Plc, United bank of Africa and Union bank. The total population for the study was two hundred and thirty one (231). The study made use of the whole due to small number. A survey design was adopted for the study. Two hundred and eleven (211) copies of questionnaire were properly completed and returned. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses with Statistical Software (SPSS). The findings indicated that influence of terms of an employment contract on the reduced expenses, collective bargaining agreement on the net interest margin and range of task on the inventory velocity of deposit money bank in Enugu State were significantly high. The study concluded that there was influence of job security on the profitability deposit money Banks in Enugu State.

Okechi, Iyke-Ofoedu & Uzochukwu (2023) conducted a study on the effect of stress management strategies on performance of employee of deposit money banks in Enugu State Nigeria. Specifically, the sought to: determine effect of counselling services strategy on employee efficiency of deposit money banks and examine effect of flextime programs strategy on employee quality service delivery of deposit money banks, the research design was descriptive survey methods. The sample size of 394 was drawn from population of 25,275 employees of 25 Banks that achieved the recapitalization requirement as at December 2021. Research questions of the study were answered using mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses stated will be tested using regression analysis. The empirical results show that counselling services strategy has significant effect employee efficiency of deposit money banks in Enugu State Nigeria (t-statistics = 7.312; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005); flextime programs strategy has significant effect on employee quality service delivery of deposit money banks in Enugu State Nigeria (t-statistics = 6.491; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005), The study concluded that there was positive and significant effect of stress management strategies on performance of employee of deposit money banks in Enugu State Nigeria.

Summary Empirical Reviews

The studies done were carried outside work engagement and employee retention of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the leadership and employee development; and communication and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the work engagement and employee retention of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state, Nigeria.

Methodology

The area of the study was the selected and international recognized banks in Abakiliki Metropolis in Ebonyi state. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The population of the study was seven hundred and twenty seven (728) staff. Ferund and Williams formula was used to get the sample size of Two hundred and fifty two (252) at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and thirty five (235) staff returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 92 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.81 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool.

Data Presentation

The relationship between leadership skills and employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi State

Table 1: Responses on the relationship between leadership skills and employee development of deposit money banks in Enugu state.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Great leadership skills empower employee to achieve their full potential	630	260	54	12	20	976	4.15	1.210	Agree
		126	65	18	6	20	235			
		53.6	27.7	7.7	2.6	8.5	100%			
2	Leaders communicate the vision and mission of the firm to employees and improve their skills.	575	296	39	38	14	962	4.09	1.184	Agree
		115	74	13	19	14	235			
		48.9	31.5	5.5	8.1	6.0	100%			
3	The continuously talent development of the employees are as a result of good leader.	445	336	39	64	17	901	3.83	1.269	Agree
		89	84	13	32	17	235			
		37.9	35.7	5.5	13.6	7.2	100%			
4	More innovation and creativity in the organisation enhanced employee learning.	490	360	39	24	22	935	3.98	1.235	Agree
		98	90	13	12	22	235			
		41.7	38.3	5.5	5.1	9.4	100%			
5	Increased productivity among the employees of the bank was due to good management.	535	320	39	20	25	939	4.00	1.283	Agree
		107	80	13	10	25	235			
		45.5	34.0	5.5	4.3	10.6	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.01	1.2362	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1, 191 respondents out of 235 representing 81.3 percent agreed that Great leadership skills empower employee to achieve their full potential 4.15 and standard deviation of 1.210. Leaders communicate the vision and mission of the firm to employees and improve their skills 189 respondents representing 80.4 percent agreed with mean score of 4.09 and standard deviation of 1.184. The continuously talent development of the employees are as a result of good leader 173 respondents representing 73.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.98 and standard

deviation of 1.235. More innovation and creativity in the organization enhanced employee learning 188 respondents representing 80.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.98 and 1.235. Increased productivity among the employees of the bank was due to good management 187 respondents representing 79.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.00 and standard deviation 1.283.

The relationship between communication and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state

Table 2: Responses on the relationship between communication and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision	
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X			
1	Effective communication promotes fewer conflicts and make happier employees	495	272	69	40	25	901	3.83	1.341	Agree	
		99	68	23	20	25	235				
		42.1	28.9	9.8	8.5	10.6	100%				
2	Team building is through proper communication and promotes employee retention.	490	244	87	32	31	884	3.76	1.397	Agree	
		98	61	29	16	31	235				
		41.7	26.0	12.3	6.8	13.2	100%				
3	Communication encourages better engagement and employee willingness to work towards a common goal.	515	240	93	30	26	904	3.85	1.344	Agree	
		103	60	31	15	26	235				
		43.8	25.5	13.2	6.4	11.1	100%				
4	Better employee relationship is ensured and support to one another.	415	228	141	20	38	842	3.58	1.419	Agree	
		83	57	47	10	38	235				
		35.3	24.3	20.0	4.3	16.2	100%				
5	A healthy organization culture is enhancing with communication and reduced turnover rates.	400	320	75	48	26	869	3.70	1.329	Agree	
		80	80	25	24	26	235				
		34.0	34.0	10.6	10.2	11.1	100%				
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.744	1.366		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2, 167 respondents out of 235 representing 71.0 percent agreed that Effective communication promotes fewer conflicts and make happier employees 3.83 and standard deviation of 1.341. Team building is through proper communication and promotes employee retention 159 respondents representing 67.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation of 1.397. Communication encourages better engagement and employee willingness to work towards common goal 163 respondents representing 69.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.344. Better employee relationship is ensured and support to one another 140 respondents representing 59.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.58 and 1.419. A healthy organization culture is enhancing with communication and reduced turnover rates 160 respondents representing 68.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.70 and standard deviation 1.329.

Test of Hypotheses

Leadership has Relationship with Employee Development of Deposit Money Banks in Ebonyi State

		Great leadership skills empower employee to achieve their full potential	Leaders communicate the vision and mission of the firm to employees and improve their skills.	The continuously talent development of the employees are as a result of good leader.	More innovation and creativity in the organisation enhanced employee learning.	Increased productivity among the employees of the bank was due to good management.
N		235	235	235	235	235
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.563	.554	.486	.550	.546
	Positive	.085	.060	.072	.094	.106
	Negative	-.563	-.554	-.486	-.550	-.546
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		8.627	8.497	7.453	8.431	8.366
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $7.453 < 8.627$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that leadership had significant position with relationship with employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $7.453 < 8.627$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Leadership had significant position with relationship with employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state.

Hypothesis Two: Communication has relationship with employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state

Table 4: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Effective communication promotes fewer conflicts and make happier employees	Team building is through proper communication and promotes employee retention.	Communication encourages better engagement and employee willingness to work towards a common goal.	Better employee relationship is ensured and support to one another.	A healthy organisation culture is enhances with communication and reduced turnover rates.
N		235	235	235	235	235
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.461	.427	.444	.353	.431
	Positive	.106	.132	.111	.162	.111
	Negative	-.461	-.427	-.444	-.353	-.431
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.061	6.540	6.801	5.414	6.605
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e. $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $5.414 < 7.061$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that Communication had significant positive relationship with employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $5.414 < 7.061$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95; percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Communication had significant positive relationship with employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value of $7.453 < 8.627$ against the critical Z- value of .000, which implies that Leadership had significant position with relationship with employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state. In the support of the result in the literature review,

From the result of hypothesis two, the calculated Z- value of $5.414 < 7.061$ against the critical Z- value of .000, which implies that Communication had significant positive relationship with employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state. In the support of the result in the literature review,

Summary of Findings

1. Leadership skills had significant position with relationship with employee development of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state, $Z(95, n = 235), 7.453 < 8.627, P < .05$.
2. Communication had significant positive relationship with employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state $Z(95, n = 235), 5.414 < 7.061, P < .05$

Conclusion

The study concluded that leadership skills and communication had significant position with relationship with employee development and employee morale of deposit money banks in Ebonyi state. Work engagement relates to the level of an employee's commitment and connection to an organization. Employee engagement has emerged as a critical driver of business success in today's competitive marketplace. High levels of engagement promote retention of talent, foster customer loyalty and improve organizational performance and stakeholder value.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management should endeavor to possess leadership skills for effective problem solving in the organizations and the opportunity to develop goods and services that set the firm apart from rivals and creating a competitive advantage.
2. Organizations should foster effective communication to facilitate the exchange of ideas and information, building relationships, fostering collaboration, increasing understanding, and achieving shared goals.

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